

The Night Watch

Robert Bilinski

— *Militia Company of District II under the Command of Captain Frans Banninck Cocq, Rembrandt van Rijn, 1642*

— *An Anatomy of the World, Wherein, by occasion of the untimely death of Mistress Elizabeth Drury, the frailty and the decay of this whole world is represented. The First Anniversary, John Donne, 1611*

We witnessed the waul of the chauvinists' call
echoing the past like prosodic vandals
intent on scorching the earth with blasted devastation
and befouling the soil for mind-dogged ends
before the turning head of the flock
could overcome its inertial distractions
whilst crudely cozened and consumed
by the supreme hedonism of the deepest conceit.

A tenebristic politic
of demagogues and paper Caesars,
dealers in vaporous oaths
ascending like liquid gold,
and the wonted addictions
of pride and duty
exploited as convictions,
descending, once we are told,
to the lies, fictions and boasts:
hosts for our new saviours; appeasers
of this noxious impolitic.

In this room, the mild-mannered miscreants
orate and propitiate grandiloquently:
their perfumed charismas forming the excipient
for anaesthetics to reside in secrecy.
Equilateral in form, scalene in mind —
rendering a narrative most dexterously —
the situationists and spinners stand behind
promising that promises are the property of the past.
And at last, this man so much maligned
hurls hounds to have the sceptic hacks
proscribed to criticise the sideshow
of his latest self-exculpatory broadcast.
For in this room men come and go,
trying to prove how much they know.

"No further, no further beyond — this man, this foreigner — for, truthfully, is he us? Can I trust a man with an iris darker than mine, from an island inferior to ours? His entire culture a simulacrum of this. If we abide the recourse itself, we abide infestation."

"I am involved in mankind," he urged.

The destroyers waste and wile the world — defiling, debasing and demeaning their conduct with counterfeited, choreographed constructs — they corrupt their campaigns, denigrate and disinform their democracies, deride and distract their dwellers, and master their malfeasant manipulants.

Watch these rebels rampage and rally on the plinths built by intemperates. The transpicuous lies of the crossfire hurricane govern the epistemic valediction: a maelstrom of parapraaxis becoming policy and the martingaling of deception, a strategy.

One evening
I sat Truth on my knees.
I found him bitter and I reviled him.

Save your pitch and yaw in these low, dishonest days for the obloquy bears no standard: standing foreshortened to enhance their little quorum — pregnant with fear and heaving with fever,

orienting their ravens on the bearings of soul-rushes
before hailing their latest, bluntest wunderkind.

These effects are charged with the deadly hissings
and the raucous music that the world, far behind us,
hurls at our Father of Truth

— He retreats.

The half-thawed men deplete the half-torn will
of the analysts, anatomists and arbitrators.
And further, their blades bleeding blunter
with every crass critique of the honing steel:
brazen backlashes and feeble frontlashes
amid the trollsters tramping in trivia.

And then this megrim of disintermediated media
maintaining its mausoleum of mundanity,
presenting postings of primatial distinction —
of pentimento opposed by impasto;
their vainglorious vision verboten
by the belittlement and blackballing
of agitators and aspersing anonymocrats.

Sincerity was their eventual deception —
their predilection
with artifice
and perception
their affection
for heraldry
and exception

the lobbyists
and socialites
as Captain
and Company

for the Old Boys
of Amsterdam

every man
is a phoenix
in the lattices of eyes
in the labyrinths of ears
upon the ramparts
of fraternity

and deepening the anatomy
advances the atrophy
slashing and blanching
and discolouring the nights.

An elegy to authenticity
in witnessing the world's infirmities —
a perennial, internal rite.
Vernissage it twice to make it night,
rejoinder with blackness of the bile:
another melancholy mercantile
of malcontentedness; and with one breath,
those twins of truth decay and yield to death.

The Donneites know a discontented man —
a dark and empty soul can understand
the frailty of the world, but nothing more.
So be a child of innocence adored,
like marble, ruby, pearls and chrysolite:

Elizabeth's essential joy excites
this world with heaven's grace and exaltates

the soul beyond of spite to contemplate
an earth abundant with commodity,
a golden girl's intense lucidity.
But even lustrousness can be ignored
by Kloveniers too noble and absorbed;
and as her emanating light reflects
upon the gloomy, tenebrous effects,
acidic stains and canvas savagery,
we see pollutants of depravity
and hear the wails of willed brutality.

If the voice of these anatomies
obscures, with darkened masculinity,
enchanted wonder and affinity
for inner sources of humanity;
and if a voice of childish levity
can disconcert our ripe sagacity,
then how to alter our proclivity
towards aggression and passivity?
A voice confronting immorality
articulated with civility:
a middle verse of rationality,
or contraverse of bright agility —
an absent voice of femininity
to resurrect our finer faculty.

Note on the cover art:

The image on the title page is an AI-generated adaptation of Rembrandt's *The Night Watch*. The figure of Captain Frans Banninck Cocq has been adapted to feature the likeness of John Donne.